

The Effectiveness of Traditional Vegetable Traders' Activities on Economists' Self-Reliance in Makassar City

(Pagandeng Study in Makassar City)

¹Patta Rapanna ; ²Yana Fajriah ; ³Nur Syamsu ; ⁴Muh Tafsir ; ⁵Didit
(Lecturer at Makassar Bongaya High School of Economic Sciences)

Abstract:- The existence of traveling vegetable vendors has a lot of positive impacts on the community such as people can meet the needs of vegetables and the like from traveling sellers, so there is no need to go shopping to the market. Mobile vegetable merchants often sell a variety of fresh vegetables and other agricultural products on mobile. The advantages of itinerant greengrocers to bring products directly to customers, flexibility in determining sales locations, and personal interaction with customers are some of the main advantages in their economic activity. However, there are also disadvantages, such as intense competition, limitations in product variety, and challenges related to regulations and changing business environments. The challenges faced by Pagandeng include intense competition, limited resources, changes in consumer behavior, and changes in the business environment. These challenges require adaptation strategies and cooperation with other stakeholders. The role of traditional peddlers in the economy of Makassar City is very important. They provide tangible benefits to society by providing easy access to everyday products. However, to remain relevant and sustainable in a changing business environment, they need to address the various challenges they face.

Keywords:- Community, People, Vegetables, Competition, Human.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the context of family economics, traditional travelling salespeople play an important role in supporting livelihoods and family income in communities around the world. They are economic agents who move from place to place to sell various goods and services to local communities. In Indonesia, traditional street vendors are often the backbone of family economics in rural and urban areas. They sell a variety of products, such as food, clothing, household goods, and even services such as household appliance repairs.

Pagandeng who ply their trade to the city, in this case Makassar City, to obtain wider opportunities and opportunities in the city because of the physical condition of

Makassar City as a place of concentration of economic, socio-cultural activities so that this city has its own charm. With a variety of job opportunities for rural communities to try their luck in the City, ranging from jobs that require intellectual thinking power to those that are simple or do not require intellectual thinking power (Sumodiningrat, 2011). It is evident that many pagandengs who sell their merchandise every day in Makassar City do not have a high educational background, only some of them have completed their education at the junior high school level (SLTP) and senior high school level (SLTA) and some even have no formal education at all.

The effectiveness of traditional street vending activities has a significant impact on the family economy. Traditional street vending can help families increase their income and create jobs, which in turn can improve the welfare of local communities. In addition, the presence of traditional vendors also allows greater access to goods and services needed by the community, especially in areas that may be far from shopping centres or fixed traditional markets.

However, despite their important role in building the economic competitiveness of families, traditional mobile vendors still face a number of challenges that may hinder their effectiveness. These challenges include aspects such as access to business capital, regulations and business licences, competition with other sellers, changes in people's consumption patterns, and changes in technology and business trends. Therefore, it is important to conduct an in-depth study on the effectiveness of traditional street vending activities and the factors that influence it.

Research on the effectiveness of traditional street vending activities has high relevance in supporting family economic development in Indonesia. Family economic development is one of the important objectives in achieving sustainable development and poverty reduction. By understanding the factors that influence the effectiveness of traditional street vending, governments, non-profit organisations and other stakeholders can design more effective policies and programmes to support them.

A. Problem Formulation

- How are the economic activities carried out by pagandeng in Makassar city
- What is the economic impact on the community of the presence of traditional pagandeng in the city of Makassar
- What are the advantages and disadvantages of pagandeng in the economic activities carried out
- What are the challenges faced by traditional pagandengs in Makassar city

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Merchant

Merchants are etymologically people who trade or can also be called merchants. So traders are people who carry out daily trading activities as their livelihood.

Damsar defines traders as follows: "a trader is a person or agency that trades products or goods to consumers either directly or indirectly". Manning and Effendi classify traders into three categories, namely;

- Punggawa is a general term used throughout South Sulawesi to describe those who have greater capital reserves in economic relations. The term is used to describe entrepreneurs who finance and organise the distribution of their own merchandise.
- Large retailers Large retailers can be divided into two groups, namely large traders who include stall entrepreneurs on the side of the road or the front corner of a house yard, and market traders who have the right to a fixed place in the official market network.
- Small retailers Small retailers include a small category around information including market traders who sell in markets, on the side of the road, as well as those who occupy stalls on the edge of large markets.

Damsar distinguishes traders according to the distribution channels of goods carried out, namely:

- Distribution Traders (Sole) are traders who hold the distribution rights for one product from a particular company.
- Party Traders (Large) are traders who buy products in large quantities which are intended to be sold to other traders such as wholesalers.
- Retail traders are traders who sell products directly to consumers. A trader is a person who trades in buying and selling goods that are not produced by himself to obtain a profit.

B. Economics

Economics is everything related to human efforts to fulfil their needs. The economy is one aspect of national life related to the fulfilment of needs for the community, including the production, distribution, and consumption of goods and services. Efforts to improve the standard of living of people individually and in groups as well as ways that are carried out in people's lives to meet their needs. Therefore, the economic aspect is very influential because it is directly involved with the community. An example is national security in the food sector. With a good economy, of course,

a country will have no difficulty in fulfilling the food needs of its citizens. Hunger will not occur and poverty can slowly decrease. In addition, a country will be very easy to apply a new technology to their agricultural system if the country has a healthy economy. The realisation of national economic resilience can be done through several sectors such as the oil and gas sector, agriculture, industry, marine, tourism, and other sectors. One sector that supports economic resilience in terms of the creative economy is the tourism sector, which can contribute when there is an economic downturn. The tourism sector as a strategic sector and a medium for integrating programmes and activities between development sectors, so that tourism is determined to be a driver of development with the main programme of tourism development in Indonesia that has been determined by the government in the Regional Medium Development Plan focused on three main programmes, namely the tourism marketing development programme, the tourism destination development programme and the partnership development programme.

C. Family Economy

In facing the reality of life that is full of challenges like today to be able to maintain and improve their standard of living, the family always develops economic aspects, until it reaches a level of life in a better order than before, namely by dividing tasks and work, in this case including the arrangement of the family economy.

Economics is the knowledge of events and issues related to human efforts individually or personally, or groups, families, ethnic groups, organisations, countries, in meeting unlimited needs faced with limited satisfying resources.

The family is an economic actor consisting of father, mother, children and other family members. Another opinion states that the family is a kinship unit which is also a unit of place marked by economic cooperation and has a function to live, socialise or educate children and help and protect the weak, especially caring for their elderly parents.

(Shinta Doriza., Mpd., M.S.E., 2015: 1) argues "Family economics is one of the larger economic study units such as companies and countries. Family economics discusses how to deal with the problem of scarce resources to satisfy the wants and needs for goods and services, so that families are required to be able to determine the choice of various kinds of activities to achieve goals".

Goenawan Sumodiningrat (in Bety Aryani 2017: 27) defines "family economics as all activities and efforts of the community or family to meet the basic needs of life, namely clothing, food, shelter, health and education".

From the above opinion, the author concludes that Family Economics is an economy developed and attempted by a family with efforts to foster interest and motivation in the field of business and skilled labour.

As well as family members who are members of the Bina Sejahtera Women Farmers Group where women have a role to help improve the family economy by joining and being active in activities in the Bina Sejahtera Women Farmers Group such as: savings and loans, oyster mushroom cultivation and yard land utilisation so that from these activities the family economy increases.

Family economic indicators are announcements, declarations, and scheduled releases of economic data based on key factors in the financial arena. Because the selected indicators will be used by cadres in the village, which in general has a relatively low level of education, to measure the degree of welfare of its members and at the same time as a guide to intervene, the indicators must not only have high validity, but also be designed in such a way that they are simple enough and operational so that they can be understood and carried out by the people in the village. On the basis of the above thoughts, the family economic indicators determined are as follows:

a. Pre-prosperous family

A family that has not been able to fulfil one or more of its 5 basic needs as a Prosperous I family, such as the need for religious instruction, food, shelter, clothing and health.

b. Prosperous Family Stage I

Are families that have been able to fulfil their basic needs at a minimum, namely :

- Performing religious worship according to the religion of each family member.
- In general, all family members eat 2 (two) times a day or more.
- All family members have different clothes for home, work/school and travelling.
- The largest part of the floor of the house is not dirt.
- When a child is sick or a couple of childbearing age wants to use family planning, they are brought to a health centre/health worker.

c. Prosperous family stage II

That is, families that, in addition to fulfilling the criteria for a prosperous family I, must also fulfil social and psychological requirements 6 to 13, namely:

- Family members worship regularly.
- The family provides meat/fish/telur and side dishes at least once a week.
- All family members get at least one new set of clothes per year.
- The floor area of the house is at least eight square metres per occupant.
- All family members are in good health once every 3 months
- At least 1 (one) aged family member has a regular income.
- All family members aged 10-60 years old can read Latin.
- If 2 or more children are living, the family has a partner of childbearing age who is using contraception (unless pregnant).

d. Prosperous Family Stage III

A family that fulfils conditions 1 to 13 and may also fulfil conditions 14 to 20, the family development conditions are:

- Have an effort to improve religious knowledge.
- Part of the family income can be set aside for family savings.
- Usually eat together at least once a day and the opportunity is used to communicate between family members.
- Participates in community activities in the neighbourhood.
- Organise recreation together outside the home at least once every 6 months.
- Can obtain news from newspapers/TV/magazines.
- Family members are able to use means of transport that are appropriate to local conditions.

e. Prosperous Family Stage III Plus Family

Which can fulfil criteria I to 20 and can also fulfil criteria 21 and 22 of the family development criteria, namely:

- Regularly or at certain times voluntarily contributing to the social activities of the community in material form.
- The Head of Family or family members are active as administrators of community associations/foundations/institutions.

f. Poor Family

Pre-prosperous families for economic reasons and KS - I families for economic reasons are unable to fulfil one or more indicators including :

1. The family eats meat, fish, eggs at least once a week.
2. In the last year, all family members acquired at least one new set of clothes.
3. The floor area of the house is at least 8 M for each occupant.

g. Very poor family

Is a pre-prosperous family for economic reasons and KS-I for economic reasons cannot meet one or more indicators which include:

- In general, all family members eat 2 times a day or more.
- Family members have different clothes for home, work/school and travel.
- The widest part of the floor is not from the ground

III. DISCUSSION

A. *How are the economic activities carried out by pagandeng in the city of Makassar*

Pagandeng is a nickname or designation of the citizens of Makassar or in Indonesian is a traveling merchant. Pagandeng is known to people who go around using bicycles with two baskets on the left and right sides and filled with piles of vegetables. In the past, people traded vegetables around using bicycles, but now pagandeng who use bicycles is rarely found, now the average pagandeng has used two-wheeled vehicles with engines, in this case the

motor in trading vegetables around with two baskets also on the left and right sides.

Pagandeng who peddle his wares to the City in this case Makassar City to obtain wider opportunities and opportunities in the city because of the physical condition of Makassar City as a place of concentration of economic, socio-cultural activities so that this city has its own charm. With a variety of job opportunities for rural people to try their luck in the city, ranging from jobs that require intellectual thinking energy to simple ones or that do not require intellectual thinking energy (Sumodiningrat, 2011). It is proven that many pagandeng every day sell their merchandise in Makassar City do not have a high educational background, only some of them complete their education at the junior high school level (SLTP) and high school (SLTA) and some even have no formal education. The goods they sell are vegetables such as spinach, long beans, kale, eggplant, penance, chili etc.

In business activities, trading business capital is one of the main and important factors that determine production activities and capacity. In this regard, the first problem that needs to be expressed in the discussion of the working system of traveling merchants is the condition of the business capital they invest in their respective trading business activities. While the average pagandeng has very limited land and limited capital which means that in working as pagandeng they depend on their own labor and the capital they have is very limited.

For pagandeng who on average have a low economic level, this system is quite helpful, because they do not need to prepare initial capital first. They simply brought the vegetables to the city, and the next day gave the proceeds to the vendors in the market that was the destination of pagandeng. Among them are some pagandeng who use a pay later system meaning that after the merchandise is sold on the market, only then the money from the sale is handed over to the merchant when it is sold out or later the next day. In general, becoming a pagandeng is not difficult because even though he does not have a percent capital, he can trade only with mutual trust capital between fellow pagandeng and farmers can already trade. A simple working system based only on mutual trust among traders. Although the work of this vegetable pagandeng looks easy, being a traveling vegetable seller still requires careful strategy and planning. Each traveling vegetable vendor has a different time and way of working, according to the creativity of each pagandeng. The time they use to carry out their business activities is only a few hours every day. in the morning until evening the traveling traders are scattered selling in various places based on their respective destinations in the city of Makassar.

In addition to the similarity of work patterns, traveling vegetable vendors have their own ways of working. The way they work is different, according to the different types of merchandise, business capacity and processing methods of each. All of them show a variety of ways and techniques of managing trades, although with patterns of using trading

times that are similar to one another. This situation also causes differences in the angle of income or income of each traveling vegetable vendor.

There are also pagandeng who make their job as a side job, meaning that pagandeng does not depend on only one job to meet the needs of his household. This is related to what was stated by Ian Scoones who revealed in his theory of livelihood strategy that the choice of livelihood strategy is largely determined by the willingness to resources and the ability to access household sources of livelihood that are very diverse (multiple source of livelihood), because if the household depends on only one job and one source of livelihood cannot meet all household needs. Therefore, pagandeng whose initial job was farming because this farmer felt that he was not enough so he took another job outside the informal sector, namely pagandeng in order to provide for his family.

The driving factors to become a traveling vegetable vendor are: it is a halal job inherited from parents, from cold produce to life and apparently can maintain the balance of nature. Environmental factors are the majority of traveling merchants, who are driven to meet the needs of life by also helping others in meeting their needs. Economic factors where gangang is able to lift the economic level of the community for the better. Especially for rice farmers (rice field owners), being a traveling trader is not just a supplement job, but as a support in obtaining housing and motorized vehicle needs. Economic factors where there are no other options to earn income to support personal and family needs, because they drop out of school and do not have a diploma

B. What is the economic impact for the community on the presence of traditional pagandeng in Makassar City

Traditional trade as a form of small business in the informal sector grows along with the development of a country, especially in developing countries. As stated by Pitoyo (2007) that the picture of the informal sector is still closely related to small-scale economic activities, less productive, has no promising prospects, the nature of businesses that tend to be independent, simple technology, small capital, and relatively unorganized. However, this sector is an alternative source of income for people who do not get job opportunities in the formal sector.

Traditional traders such as itinerant vegetable vendors as a form of informal sector business still survive in the midst of competition with modern markets that are developing today. According to BPS (2019), along with the development of modern markets such as shopping centers and supermarkets with complete infrastructure facilities and comfort facilities, consumers have met many of their needs from modern markets. Runtu et al., (2018) define the modern market as a place to buy goods comfortably and cleanly and the products sold are diverse and have good quality. The modern market is growing rapidly in Indonesia's urban areas. As stated by (Schipmann & Qaim, 2011) that modern markets such as modern retail are growing rapidly in many developing countries. Competition

with modern markets, be it supermarkets or modern retail that provides comfort and good quality, is something that cannot be avoided by traditional traders such as traveling vegetable vendors. Itinerant vegetable traders certainly have special characteristics or strategies in the system of economic transactions with consumers so that they can survive to this day.

The presence of traders in the city of Makassar or in any city can have a significant economic impact on the community. This impact can vary depending on the type of trader, location, and characteristics of the market. Based on research conducted by Vi'in Ayu Pertiwi (2020), the driving factors that cause people to make purchases at traveling vegetable vendors are influenced by factors of friendliness and familiarity with traders. This is true, in fact, as it is known that people as consumers when shopping at mobile vegetable vendors are accompanied by chatting with both merchants and other consumers. As the results of research (Handoyo, 2012) which states that one of the norms developed by traveling vegetable vendors is to serve customers as friendly as possible in the sense of hospitality and effective communication that also facilitates the business of traveling vegetable vendors. This attraction is what consumers do not get when shopping in modern markets. With mechanisms up to standard, the modern market does not offer a system of familiarity with buyers. Another case with traditional traders such as traveling vegetable vendors who offer familiarity, one of the advantages is the increasing number of consumers who become customers.

In fact, itinerant greengrocers not only prioritize familiarity and friendliness but also price and market factors, product freshness, retail services, and credit services. Price is certainly one of the factors considered by consumers. Meanwhile, the market referred to here is caused by homes that are far from traditional markets in this case as competitors or complementary. According to Muftiadi & Maulina (2016), people can meet the needs of vegetables and the like from traveling sellers, so there is no need to go shopping to the market. Mobile vegetable merchants often sell a variety of fresh vegetables and other agricultural products on mobile. This increases the accessibility of agricultural products for the community, especially in areas that may be far from traditional markets or supermarkets. Thus, people can easily meet their nutritional needs without having to travel far.

On small or daily purchases, many households tend to prefer to buy from traveling merchants. Because itinerant vegetable vendors sell and eat every day, the products sold are certainly in fresh condition. The consistency of product freshness every day is one of the considerations for consumers in making purchases at traveling vegetable vendors. Furthermore, consumers are also quite considerate of retail services where purchases do not have to be in large quantities. This is due to consumers who purchase food needs at mobile vegetable vendors almost every day by considering the daily household menu. Another factor that makes it more attractive to buy daily food needs at mobile

vegetable vendors turns out to be credit / debt services or what is often called cash bonds. By prioritizing the satisfaction of their customers, traveling greengrocers often offer debt services. As stated by Handoyo (2012) that the debt system carried out is for known buyers who are often unable to pay, so usually traders trust and provide opportunities to pay the next day. This buying and selling practice works well because of mutual trust between merchants and buyers or customers.

Some of these factors are believed by traveling vegetable traders to be able to encourage consumers or customers to decide to buy daily food needs at mobile vegetable vendors. Commensurate with what was stated by Kotler and Keller in Tjiptono & Chandra (2012) explained that consumers' decisions to make purchases are determined by the choice of the dealer. This means that buyers make decisions about which dealer or seller to choose based on factors such as location, price, inventory and others. Even though they have to compete with the rapid development of modern markets that offer various facilities, the fact is that the people of Malang City are still loyal to meet their kitchen needs from traveling vegetable vendors. It can be believed that itinerant greengrocers as informal sector businesses have different marketing strategies than modern markets. In accordance with the theory, Kotler & Keller (2016) that "Marketing is meeting needs profitability". In this case, itinerant vegetable vendors carry out marketing strategies where to meet the needs and mutual benefits of each other.

C. What are the advantages and disadvantages of the pagandengs in the economic activity carried out

The economy of a country is closely related to the role of economic actors, both those operating on a large and small scale. In the realm of microeconomics, the role of itinerant vegetable vendors is integral in efforts to meet the daily needs of the community. Itinerant greengrocers, as we find them in various urban and rural corners, have a significant role to play in the local economic ecosystem.

Fulfillment of existing demand must be followed by the availability of vegetables through cultivation activities carried out by farmers. The need for these vegetables requires farmers to be able to produce with the quantity and quality desired by the market. The need for vegetables for the community is closely related to the need for nutrition for the health of the community itself. Vegetables are the main source of nutritional fulfillment. Each vegetable will provide different nutritional benefits, so the fulfillment of vegetables in a balanced manner is very necessary.

In everyday life, we often see itinerant greengrocers strolling around settlements, bringing various kinds of fresh vegetables and other agricultural products. They are part and parcel of the local economic landscape, and their role in providing direct access to agricultural products to communities cannot be ignored. The presence of itinerant greengrocers has long been a hallmark of urban and rural life.

Itinerant greengrocers are a vivid example of micro-enterprises thriving in the traditional way, selling a variety of agricultural products, including fresh vegetables, fruits, and in some cases, processed groceries. They operate with high mobility, visiting various locations such as residential areas, traditional markets, and other strategic places. Their existence is a convenient access solution for people who may find it difficult to access traditional markets or supermarkets.

However, as is the case with many business models, the existence of a traveling greengrocer also has good and bad sides that need to be understood. Advantages include increased accessibility of agricultural products, increased family income, and diversification of consumption. Meanwhile, deficiencies include issues such as lack of regulation, health and hygiene issues, and social and environmental issues. Here are the advantages of traveling vegetable vendors:

➤ *Has High Mobility*

High mobility allows itinerant greengrocers to efficiently reach different groups of customers in different locations. They can tailor their routes based on knowledge of demand patterns and customer presence in different regions. For example, they might visit morning markets, then switch to office areas during the day, and then to residential complexes in the afternoon or evening. The ability to tailor sales locations to customer behavior is one of the main attractions of itinerant greengrocers.

➤ *Personalized Service*

Mobile greengrocers often have a closer relationship with customers compared to larger supermarkets or traditional markets. They often identify customers by name, food preferences, and purchase history. This allows them to provide more relevant advice and recommendations. For example, if a customer likes to eat organic vegetables, the merchant can suggest products that match those preferences. This personalized service often creates a sense of customer trust and loyalty.

➤ *Flexibility in Time and Location*

Itinerant greengrocers can manage their sales times and locations more flexibly. They may operate at times that suit customer needs, such as in the afternoon when most people have finished work or near school when children come home. The ability to present yourself in strategic places, such as near offices or schools, is an added advantage in approaching customers.

➤ *Access to Fresh Produce*

The products offered by itinerant greengrocers are often fresh produce that has just been harvested or arrived from local farmers. This means customers can buy vegetables and fruits in very fresh conditions, which may not always be the case in larger traditional markets. The quality of this fresh product is the main attraction for customers who want to include healthy foods in their diet.

➤ *Social Interaction*

Shopping from a traveling greengrocer often creates a more intimate social interaction between vendor and customer. Customers can talk to merchants about their food preferences, exchange stories, or simply interact with vendors in ways that may not be the case in larger shopping environments. These more personalized interactions can create a more positive and memorable shopping experience.

In addition to having advantages, in the traveling vegetable vendor business, there are also disadvantages. Here are the drawbacks:

➤ *High Level of Competition*

Due to the mobile nature of vegetable vendors' mobility, the level of competition between them can be very high in some regions. This can result in significant price fluctuations and lack of income stability for traders. Intense competition can also force traders to sell products at low prices, which can affect their profits.

➤ *Dependence on Weather and Seasons*

Itinerant greengrocers are often highly dependent on weather conditions and seasons. Natural disasters, climate change, or extreme summers can impact the availability and quality of agricultural products. This can be a challenge in maintaining supply consistency.

➤ *Environmental Impact*

The use of single-use packaging, such as plastic, in a traveling greengrocer's business can have a negative impact on the environment. The resulting plastic waste can pollute the environment and contribute to larger environmental problems.

➤ *Unguaranteed Product Quality and Cleanliness*

Some mobile greengrocers may not have adequate storage or transportation facilities, which may result in a deterioration in the quality of agricultural products. In addition, hygiene-related problems, such as unhygienic handling, can be serious. This can threaten consumer health and reduce trust in the products sold.

D. What are the challenges faced by traditional pagandeng in the city of Makassar

In this modern era, the trade sector has experienced rapid development, especially in big cities such as Makassar. Various forms of trade, from large retailers to small traders, play an important role in the local economy. In this context, traditional merchants selling various products around have become an indispensable element of the urban landscape.

The city of Makassar, as one of the major trading centers in Indonesia, witnessed rapid growth in the trade sector, which included traveling merchants. These peddlers, often referred to as "pagandeng," had a very significant role in providing a wide range of consumer goods, from food to daily necessities. However, behind their deep presence in people's daily lives, there are a number of challenges that must be faced. In this environment, pagandengs keep their traditions and cultural heritage, while striving to survive and

thrive in an ever-changing era. In the era of globalization, urbanization, and lifestyle changes, these peddlers are faced with various problems that affect the sustainability of their businesses. These challenges include economic, social, and environmental aspects. Here are the usual challenges faced by itinerant vegetable vendors: :

➤ *Change of Demand*

Market demand for vegetables can vary over time. Several factors, such as seasonality, dietary trends, and changes in consumer preferences can affect product demand. Itinerant greengrocers must always monitor market trends to adjust product offerings in order to meet customer needs and desires.

➤ *Operating Costs*

Mobile vegetable business capital is used for operational costs, such as purchasing stock, fuel, vehicle maintenance, and promotional costs. Limited capital, transportation, and storage facilities can limit the ability of itinerant greengrocers to expand their businesses. Merchants may be limited in terms of purchasing inventory in bulk or having suitable vehicles to transport their merchandise. Solutions may involve cooperation between merchants to share resources or seek additional funding.

➤ *Lack of Regulation*

The absence of adequate regulation or weak enforcement can create business uncertainty. Mobile greengrocers may not have clear guidelines or responsibilities to adhere to stable health, hygiene, or pricing standards. This can lead to price fluctuations and uncertainty for consumers.

➤ *Social and Environmental Challenges:*

The presence of mobile greengrocers can create social challenges, such as traffic jams at their sales locations, and hygiene problems around their establishments. The use of single-use plastic packaging can also contribute to the problem of plastic waste and environmental impact. Traders can collaborate with authorities and communities to address these social and environmental issues.

Overcoming these challenges requires adaptation, innovation, and cooperation between traders, governments, and other stakeholders.

IV. CONCLUSION

Pagandeng is a nickname or designation of the citizens of Makassar or in Indonesian is a traveling merchant. Pagandeng is known to people who go around using bicycles with two baskets on the left and right sides and filled with piles of vegetables. In the past, people traded vegetables around using bicycles, but now pagandeng who use bicycles is rarely found, now the average pagandeng has used two-wheeled vehicles with engines, in this case the motor in trading vegetables around with two baskets also on the left and right sides.

The existence of traveling vegetable vendors has a lot of positive impacts on the community such as people can meet the needs of vegetables and the like from traveling sellers, so there is no need to go shopping to the market. Mobile vegetable merchants often sell a variety of fresh vegetables and other agricultural products on mobile. The advantages of itinerant greengrocers to bring products directly to customers, flexibility in determining sales locations, and personal interaction with customers are some of the main advantages in their economic activity. However, there are also disadvantages, such as intense competition, limitations in product variety, and challenges related to regulations and changing business environments. The challenges faced by Pagandeng include intense competition, limited resources, changes in consumer behavior, and changes in the business environment. These challenges require adaptation strategies and cooperation with other stakeholders.

The role of traditional peddlers in the economy of Makassar City is very important. They provide tangible benefits to society by providing easy access to everyday products. However, to remain relevant and sustainable in a changing business environment, they need to address the various challenges they face.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Puspitasari, D., & Indraswari, K. (2020). Analysis of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises of Mobile Traditional Market Traders in Surakarta City. *Journal of Social and Agricultural Economics*, 13(1), 27-34.
- [2]. Jambeck, J. R., et al. (2015). Plastic waste inputs from land into the ocean. *Science*, 347(6223), 768-771.
- [3]. Kuncoro, A. (2017). Informal Economy, Street Vendors and Urban Poverty in Indonesia. *Indonesian Journal of Geography*, 49(1), 15-28.
- [4]. Rifai, A., Rokhana, D., & Utami, W. (2021). Food safety knowledge and practices of street food vendors in Semarang City, Indonesia. *Food Control*, 124, 107907.
- [5]. Rahman, Abdul. 2022. "Pagandeng: A Study of the Economic Activities of Vegetable Traders in Panciro Village"
- [6]. Suhariah, S. 2020. "CHAPTER II THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS, FRAME OF MIND"
- [7]. Rismawidiawati. 2016. "PAQGANDENG MUSLIM'S DEVOTION IN SERVING THE NEEDS OF THE PEOPLE OF MAKASSAR CITY 1997-2005"
- [8]. Vi'in Ayu Pertiwi. 2020. "FACTORS INFLUENCING CONSUMERS TO MAKE PURCHASES AT MOBILE GREENGROCERS (MLIJO)"
- [9]. Hidayatiningsih, Eka Nurainy. 2020. "INCOME ANALYSIS OF ITINERANT VEGETABLE TRADERS AND RESIDENT VEGETABLE TRADERS IN PALANGKA RAYA CITY"
- [10]. Bisniz.id. 2023. "Business selling vegetables around, opportunities, weaknesses, risks and strategies"

- [11]. Sinta. 2023. "Mobile Vegetable Business: Opportunities and Challenges (Beginners Must Know!)"
- [12]. Marlinah, lilies. 2017. "Increasing National Economic Resilience through Creative Economy Development"